

8T – Creation of a Universe Packet

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September 1, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing the second representation of the main equation of the 8T, it is possible to construct a more accurate version of the Universe packet. In particular, it is possible to predict the number of universes in the packet is even.

The packet is constructed by infinite number of pairs, or a finite number of pairs with opposite curvature orientation. Than the summation of all universe packets is presented to reach the multiverse.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matrix tensor M , given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matrix tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron by putting it in the fine structure constant formula:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We have described the arbitrary variations of the manifold by the term on the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matric tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

We have presented the spin classification in the 8T thesis, page seventeen, while using the prime critical line:

Spin 0: $2N_0$ variations

Spin $\frac{1}{2}$: $2N_0 + 3$ variations

Spin 1: $2N_0 + 3 + N_V$ variations

Spin $N = 2N_0 + 3 + N_{V1} + N_{V2} \dots$ variations

Up to this point was introduction, reader is probability familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. **From here** on out, we have a completely **new paper**. let us examine the equation (1.2) which meant to express the idea of infinite amount of universes interacting with each other.

$$\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0$$

The second term indicate that there are more universes with negative orientation of curvature than the inverse orientation given by the first term. To create a flat universe packet we need infinite amount of pairs with opposite orientation that is as presented in the 8T thesis:

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_2} = 0$$

However, instead of equalizing into zero, we can parametrize the equation and consider it as a universe pair, the packet than is considered as the summation of all the universe pairs.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_2} = \mathfrak{Z}_1$$

$$\mathfrak{Z}_1 + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \mathfrak{Z}_1 = 0 \quad (2.A)$$

So the idea is to represent the packet as the summation of universe pairs with opposite curvature orientation flattening each other, the universe packet according to this idea is infinite but contain an even number of universes, i.e. manifolds flattening each other. That is because we need an even number of manifolds with inverse curvature orientation. Another way of representation is to vary the equation (1.1):

$$\sum_{m=1}^K \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^K \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2.A)$$

When those equations were originally derived, the idea was to present the infinite packet as presented in equation (1.1). However, (1.2.A) and (2.A) are representing more accurate form of description as to how the packet is constructed, how much manifolds it must contain, i.e. an even number aspiring infinity with opposite curvature orientation. In addition to how it was possibly created. The packet was possibly created as a result of universe pairs which interact with each via areas of extremum curvatures, **at first only with each other**. Those two universes as they interact flatten each other causing outward acceleration from those extremum curvatures. Later they join to another universe inverse dual to form a packet of four which flatten each other and so on, endlessly. Those pairs could cluster immediately or gradually toward the growing packet which will contain even amount of universes, as a set of pairs flattening each other. That is in agreement with the demand of the stationary on the Lorentz manifold presented in the beginning of 8T thesis. So according to this idea, the parameter K is an even:

$$2 | K$$

One final point, equation (2.A) represent the pairs within one universe packet considered infinite. It could be finite and than the structure of the multiverse is the summation of all the packets. That is by:

$$\mathfrak{Z}_1 + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \mathfrak{Z}_1 = \mathcal{D}_1 \quad (1.2B)$$

$$\mathcal{D}_1 + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \mathcal{D}_n = \mathcal{M} \quad (1.2C)$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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